

Integrated Social Information Engineering

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Abstract

Recognizing that a community's capability to respond to and recover from disaster depends partly on the strength and effectiveness of its social networks, social network analysis (SNA) has risen to a field having important implications. In particular, many disaster and emergency recovery operations now consider the information provided by social networks to be one of their prime sources of data. The task of integrated social information engineering is to fuse that data to yield meaningful knowledge devoid of contradiction and provide a pathway for discovery of related information. Computing with Words represents an attempt to fuse linguistic information using possibilistic analysis. The approach entails machine learning that fuses contexts consisting of essentially symbolic information for the prediction of an appropriate action(s). SNA is facilitated because the method allows large contexts and crowd sourced approaches, consisting of distinct textual phrases, to be mapped to similar prior experiential knowledge. If this knowledge proves to be erroneous for any reason, then it is a simple matter to supply the correct knowledge for non monotonic learning to occur. The method also supplies an associated possibility, allows for proper responses to be forthcoming, and can be trained / run in parallel. In summary, the paper proper considers the burgeoning field of social information engineering and the automation of its integration by way of transformative reuse.

Keywords: Computing with Words, Data Fusion, Information Integration, Reuse, Social Network Analysis

1. Introduction

Our planet where we seek peace, prosperity, and economic security incurs frequent and often unpredictable disasters and extreme events wreaking havoc on homes, businesses and the environment.

Natural disasters such as earthquakes, heat waves, floods, volcanoes, super typhoons, tsunamis, blizzards, landslides, and droughts killed at least a quarter million people in 2010. More people were killed worldwide by natural disasters last year than have been killed in terrorism attacks in the past 40 years combined. "The Earth strikes back in cahoots with bad human decision-making," said Debarati Guha Sapir, director for the World

Health Organization's Centre for Research. According to the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre, about 42 million people were forced to flee their homes because of natural disasters around the world in 2010, more than double the number during the previous year.

Man-made technological catastrophes such as BP's busted oil well caused 172 million gallons to gush out into the Gulf of Mexico. Japan's Fukushima Daiichi nuclear plant released a total amount of radiation of 770,000 terabecquerels (NISA) into the atmosphere in the first week of the crisis displacing 47,000 nuclear refugees in shelters across Japan. Mining disasters trapped men deep in the Earth and caused dozens of deaths in tragic collapses in West Virginia, China, and New Zealand. Disasters have a direct impact on economic output, with the emerging role of globalization and just-in-time manufacturing no community is immune to disasters and no community is an island unto itself, all individuals and communities are interdependent [1].

The intensity and frequency of extreme events and disasters is on the rise. In order to withstand and recover from natural and human-caused disasters it is essential that the private and public sectors, citizens and communities, work together to anticipate threats, limit their effects, and rapidly restore functionality after a crisis. Collaboration synergy is predicated on the notion that individuals and organizations that work together will accomplish more than can be accomplished on their own. Sharing of information is critical to the preparation for and response to emergencies. "We must increase collaborative efforts to prevent displacement by natural disasters, and do a better job of protecting those displaced," said Elisabeth Rasmusson, the secretary general of the Norwegian Refugee Council.

During disasters, having access to social information is critical to response and recovery as having access to essential items like food and safe drinking water. Knowing how and where to receive social information can save lives during and after severe weather events and stressful situations. Through SNA, analysis of social relationships allows practitioners to identify and characterize relevant social networks, isolate ways to improve community resilience and to improve the quality and speed of critical decision-making processes during a disaster or emergency. The study of complex human systems and SNA can reveal the structure of existing

networks so that networks can be designed or improved for the purpose of building community resilience

2. Need for Social Information in Disaster and Emergency Response

Former President Bush issued an executive order for departments of the executive branch to cooperate and share information. The Obama administration continues stressing the need for an open government that collaborates more with the public and agencies that can embrace social networking tools and information sharing more actively. The culture to shift from an information paradigm based on "need to know" to "need to share" tends to increase information availability and extend data availability. Disaster resilience correlates strongly with community resilience therefore sectors in the private/public industry must collaborate in order to identify gaps in knowledge and practice to build and strengthen community level disaster resilience.

Multifaceted emergency operations generally involve multilateral action from multiple military and civilian agencies. Operation and maintenance of many community assets including critical infrastructure continue to be in private hands. To better understand the connectivity of critical sectors of the community for information exchange, integration and interoperability to overcome geographic distribution and infrastructure heterogeneity civil authorities and emergency managers need social information to analyze and display social network information.

A better understanding of social information can sort out appropriate role behavior and enable spatial relationship mapping to physical attributes of geography and terrain, the built environment, critical infrastructures, key resources, proximity of segments of the population/neighborhoods to local hazards to form the most complete, accurate, and timely picture of situations as they evolve.

During non-emergency times, disaster and emergency response teams adhere to standardized and established procedures. Research has illustrated to us time and again that during emergencies, external and/or internal dynamics create enough stress so that responding agencies operate in a state of crisis [2].

Improved emergency management and planning is facilitated through the increased flow of information via communication and trust, dependable social data and a defined social network structure. The demanding and time-sensitive nature of emergency response, communication and decision-making are key facets in the process of adequately and rapidly addressing these events.

3. An Approach for SNA-Fusing with Words

"CBFER" a Java program written by Dr. Stuart Rubin submitted for patent, is a system for case-based reasoning (CBR) which maps situations onto actions providing a

whole new way of capturing social networks in much richer structures than raw graphs. It embodies a capability for mapping the semantics of sentences enabling social data enrichment and characterizing the structure of a social network, its strategic positions, and the way information flows. It does not extract keywords, count keywords or sequences of keywords in mapping the semantics of a sentence or phrase. Rather, it learns to create a heuristic version space for every word in the sentence updating bounds as evidence increases. After all, while prepositions can be ignored most of the time, the word, "A" cannot be ignored in say, Vitamin A.

The meaning of a sentence is derived from the meaning of each of its words, where the meaning of each word is derived from that of each word that appears in its context, which is a system parameter. Then, the meaning of a context, which consists of one or more phrases (sentences), is derived by similar process, which finds the case onto which it best maps. Here, the number of phrases (sentences) in the context need not be in 1:1 correspondence with those in the cases. The aforementioned contextual matching process allows for the difference in cardinality. The end result is a system, which learns to heuristically map the meaning of a context (and thereby derive the proper action(s), if any) by what we humans loosely call analogy. Moreover, this mapping process is able to do so using natural language. This means that it is ideally suited to solving problems involving SNA.

One key point needs to be emphasized; namely, its methodology requires on the order of person-years of training to minimize the incidence of domain-specific errors. However, the method is fully amenable to parallel realization. Thus, years of training may be completed in days.

What follows is a simulated run of the actual CBFER program (Figs. 1a, 1b). While the database has been cold-started, it's believed that the example is sufficient to hint at the inherent potential of the algorithm.

Use keywords instead of NL sentences for improved learning performance. Enter exactly one concept per line. Thus, enter "white Toyota Camry.", or "electric bill.", or "movie theatre ticket.", or "sunlight."

Use a ctrl+b to interrupt:

Enter (multiline) context or "e" to exit:

CNN says a tornado is approaching. Where do we go for shelter?

No exact crispy match of the context was found in the case base. The best fuzzy match of the context was found at case number 0. The possibility = 0.125 over [0, 1], or [no match, perfect match].

The best fuzzily-matched case antecedent was found to be:

The Weather Channel Tornado outbreak warning issued for all of Northwest Texas. Residents advised to seek shelter and listen for emergency civil defense broadcasts.

-coa-

The associated consequent was found to be: **If you have a storm cellar go there. If not, go to the nearest locality having one – such as a school, church, etc. Do not waste time!**

-eoc-

Is this the correct consequent for the current context (y)? Y

Words file successfully updated with 53 entries. The CbferCases file was updated with 2 case(s).

Fig. 1a CBFER for simulated recovery from a Tornado – Initial Performance

Enter (multiline) context or "e" to exit: I'm carrying a child. Can I outrun the twister?

No exact crispy match of the context was found in the case base. The best fuzzy match of the context was found at case number 2. The possibility = 0.114 over [0, 1], or [no match, perfect match].

The best fuzzily-matched case antecedent was found to be:

A car windshield was broken by golf-ball sized hail. Electric power lines are down. I hear the sound of freight trains. The twister has an eerie green glow. Homes in the twister's path are exploding.
-coa-

The associated consequent was found to be:

Run at right angles to the tornado's path. Do not seek shelter under an overpass. Get as low as you can to avoid flying debris. Stay away from downed power lines. Don't panic!
-coc-

Fig. 1b CBFER for simulated recovery from a Tornado – Improving performance over a larger base

4. SNA in Disaster and Emergency Response

SNA is based on the intuitive notion that the relationships among interacting units are important [3]. Through aid of approaches such as fusing with words and CBFER, users can review the data visually (constructing a sociogram in form of nodes and edges) and statistically to better identify and exploit key features of social networks to manage their life cycles and predict their evolution. Nodes can represent any social or cultural entity such as people, partners and units of action, resources, facilities, organizations, departments, skills, ideas, cities, states, countries, and events [3]. Edges can represent the physical avenues of transportation and communication, such as roads, sea lanes, rivers, flight paths, phone lines, or fiber-optic cables. Edges can also signify intangible social, political or cultural connections and relationships, such as associations, alliances, authority lines, precedence, and transfer of resources, friendships or group bias [4]. Capturing social networks helps in understanding the nonlinear nature of many relationships in a network and identifying tipping points, centers of gravity or critical events during a disaster-relief effort clarifying the optimal communication and enlistment methods for intervention-based action.

Employing SNA creates a context to capture the configuration and multiplicity of social ties for socio-demographic, behavioral, intrapersonal characteristics to better understand the homophily in social relationships and illustrate strengths and divisions in network relationships. It creates a context for an individual's typical social network, geographic propinquity, families, organizations, activation and mobilization of their relationships and the impact of a broad range of social support in disaster contexts under extreme events.

For the purpose of building community resilience, SNA exposes network structures assisting civil authorities and emergency planners determine how flexibility can be fostered to improve information flow and enable effective planning, coordination and communication between and within organizations. SNA improves improvisational response through the identification of new means for coordination and/or influence information involved in disaster and emergency response under uncertainty [3].

When networks have strong ties with a large number of organizations to include community and military organizations, greater network resilience during a disaster is more than likely to result. Therefore, SNA can have positive effects on the likelihood of a successful timely response and recovery to a disaster [4].

5. Conclusions

This paper has taken a look at social information engineering – the what, why, and who of social networking and developed an approach for SNA. This approach – *Fusing with Words* – can aid in computing the meaning of natural language phrases and sentences in context through non monotonic learning. Learning time is polynomial unlike the case for say neural networks, which are *NP-hard* given the inherent hidden layer. Moreover, Fusing with Words is well-suited to making sense out of information derived from social networks and the methodology can be trained using massive parallelism. This means that it can learn from thousands of analysts at the same time – a socially engineered method in its own right.

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